

SPORTS TRAINER PSYCHOLOGICAL CHARACTERISTICS OF THE PERSONALITY AND ACTIVITIES OF FREEL WRESTLERS

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Abstract This article analyzes the personal and professional psychological characteristics of freestyle wrestling athletes, their emotional states before and during competitions, motivation levels, and the psychological aspects of coaching activities. It also examines the influence of a sports coach on the athlete's psyche, their role in developing volitional qualities, and effective pedagogical and psychological approaches.

Keywords: freestyle wrestling, sports psychology, motivation, emotional state, coach, willpower, stress, psychological preparation.

Introduction

A sports coach is not only a teacher of sports techniques but also a leader who directly influences an athlete's personal and psychological development. His activities are aimed not only at improving the athlete's physical fitness but also at strengthening mental stability, forming motivation, and developing personal qualities. Taking into account the individual psychological characteristics of each athlete, the coach helps them fully realize their potential and develop skills for making correct decisions under stress and pressure.

From the perspective of sports psychology, an athlete's personality depends not only on their athletic performance but also on the team environment, competitiveness, endurance, and internal discipline. Therefore, sports coaches are not only specialists in managing physical fitness but also psychological leaders. Their pedagogical and psychological approaches significantly influence an athlete's self-confidence, strategies for achieving success, and personal motivation.

Within the framework of this topic, the psychological influence of sports coaches on the personality and performance of athletes, the athlete's mental state and its dependence on performance, as well as the importance of effective coach-athlete communication, are scientifically analyzed. This analysis serves to understand how the psychological knowledge and pedagogical competencies of sports coaches influence the personal development of athletes.

The main task of upbringing is to form stable moral qualities in students, socially acceptable behavior, and to guide athletes toward their goals. In this process, the coach positively influences the mental, moral, and physical

development of athletes through personal example and pedagogical influence. From this perspective, the profession of a sports coach is primarily a pedagogical activity. Sport is one of the most effective means of social upbringing, and the educational role of the coach is particularly important in working with young athletes. The coaching profession has its own characteristics, which are manifested in the following factors:

Motivational leadership - a coach should not force their students to engage in training, but rather inspire them, motivate them, and awaken their own interest.

Constant and close pedagogical contact - a sports coach spends more time with his students than a school teacher. During training sessions, competitions, and training camps, the coach not only focuses on sports indicators but also participates in the educational process.

Personal example and authority - young athletes perceive their coaches as an ideal and absolutely trust their opinions. Therefore, the moral reputation and personal qualities of a coach are of great importance.

Creative approach and innovation - effective coaching activities require research, experimentation, and the implementation of new pedagogical methods. A creative approach in the process of developing athletes leads to effective results.

Methodological thoroughness - often a coach is forced to teach athletes technical movements that they cannot perform themselves. Therefore, it is necessary to thoroughly master teaching methods and have a clear didactic orientation.

Emotional resilience and stress resistance - coaching activities are often associated with intense psychological and physical exertion, requiring decision-making in extreme conditions during competitions.

A coach must possess a high level of psychological qualities in their activities. These features include:

Focus and sensitivity - the coach must be able to analyze an athlete's individual characteristics and clearly identify their weaknesses and strengths. Quick and clear thinking - making quick decisions in sports conditions is important.

A coach must possess tactical and strategic thinking.

A high level of psychological adaptability is the ability to withstand stress and emotional strain arising during the sports process.

Culture and effectiveness of speech - the coach's words must be motivating, understandable, and clear. Honesty, logical consistency, and emotional expressiveness have a positive effect on athletes.

Coaching is not just about teaching sports techniques, but also a pedagogical creative process. Research indicates that creative mentors possess the following characteristics:

An innovative approach in the educational process is to influence not only the physical but also the moral and intellectual development of athletes.

Ability to experiment and experiment - a desire to introduce new methods and strategies.

Independent thinking and decision-making - a coach must be able to solve complex pedagogical situations.

Ability to work in a team and individually - to work effectively with athletes, an individual approach and an understanding of group psychology are necessary.

The effectiveness of communication between a sports coach and an athlete directly affects athletic results. It is important for the coach to convey their thoughts in a clear, understandable, and motivational manner. The following qualities of speech are of particular pedagogical importance:

Clarity and clear expressiveness - for athletes to easily perceive the coach's instructions, they must speak logically and clearly.

Logical consistency - during the training process, the coach's words and practical actions must correspond to each other.

Emotional sensitivity - the coach must be able to provide athletes with positive energy and exert a strong influence on their psyche.

Sports coaching is a process that involves not only enhancing physical fitness but also providing psychological education, motivating athletes, and developing their social adaptability. For athletes, a coach should be not only a mentor but also a psychologist, a leader, and a motivational leader. Therefore, a pedagogical approach, psychological preparation, and personal example play an important role in coaching activities. The use of creative approaches and innovative methods contributes to the improvement of sports results.

Violations of pedagogical tact in the activities of sports coaches often occur during interactions with athletes. Such problems can negatively affect the effectiveness of communication between the coach and the athlete. Pedagogical ambiguities, incorrect communicative strategies, and errors in educational approaches can reduce athletes' motivation and undermine their psychological stability.

The main communication errors encountered in the pedagogical activities of coaches are:

Deviation from the average balance (chatterboxing or excessive reprimands) - during training and competitions, a coach can reduce performance by talking to athletes excessively, giving them too many reprimands, or keeping them under pressure.

Excessive severity or rudeness - excessive demandingness, severity in dealing with athletes, or the use of unpleasant words in unexpected situations can have a negative impact on an athlete's mental state.

Emotional imbalance and short communication - disregarding athletes' inner emotions, treating them with indifference, and being excessively short in communication can reduce athletes' motivation.

A stereotyped pedagogical approach—the confinement of teaching and upbringing methods to a specific framework—can hinder the development of athletes.

Incorrect assessment and excessive praise or criticism—overemphasizing the achievements of some athletes while ignoring others, or conversely, repeating constant shortcomings—can evoke a sense of inequality among athletes.

Incorrect verbal and physical communication - when the coach's words and his practical actions do not match - can cause distrust among athletes.

Using incorrect terminology and jargon - deviating from official sports terminology or using informal jargon - can negatively impact a coach's level of professionalism.

A coach's social reputation depends on their personal and professional qualities and is based on the following factors:

Honesty and truthfulness are an objective and fair approach to athletes.

Creative and innovative approach - the implementation of new methods during training and competitions.

Analytical thinking and observation - accurately assessing the individual capabilities of athletes and developing their development strategies.

Intuition and psychological sensitivity - understanding the mental state of athletes and developing appropriate approaches.

Patience and stress resilience - a coach must be able to control themselves in extreme conditions and make effective decisions under psychological pressure.

Initiative and leadership qualities - inspiring and motivating athletes through leadership qualities.

The coach must effectively utilize their communicative skills and management strategies when influencing the athletes. In sports psychology, coaching styles are divided into three main types:

Authoritarian (autocratic) style - the coach sets high requirements for his students, gives them strict orders, and makes decisions independently. Although this method increases discipline in some athletes, it can increase mental stress during long-term work and limit creative thinking.

Democratic style - the coach works in collaboration with athletes, takes their opinions into account, and applies an interactive approach during the training process. This method serves to develop athletes' ability to make independent decisions and work in a team.

Liberal (free) style - the coach gives the athletes freedom and encourages them to act independently. While this approach is effective for some individual athletes, it can cause problems in team sports. A coach's professional success depends not only on teaching athletes technical skills but also on positively influencing their psychological development. Proper pedagogical communication and effective communication enhance a coach's reputation and strengthen the motivation of athletes. The application of appropriate approaches, taking into account the individual characteristics of the athletes, is the responsibility of the coach.

will serve to increase the efficiency of its activities.

Management styles in coaching activities and their impact on the psychological development of athletes

The coach utilizes various psychological and pedagogical approaches when managing a sports team. Each of them has a different impact on athletes' motivation, psychological stability, social adaptation, and athletic performance. In sports psychology, management styles are divided into three main forms: autocratic (authoritarian), liberal (laxistic), and democratic.

1. Autocratic (authoritarian) management style

The autocratic management style incorporates full control by the coach, requiring all decisions to be made independently. In this method, the coach uses strict commands, demands, and directives in the process of leadership.

Psychological characteristics of autocratic rule:

Centralized management - the coach makes all decisions independently and demands unconditional obedience from the athletes.

Limitations in personal relationships are observed - remote contact with athletes, and a weak emotional connection.

Psychological pressure and criticism - a coach may severely criticize athletes in cases of failure, and sometimes use harsh words.

Separating athletes closer to oneself - There is a tendency to highlight the "leading" athletes in a team, which can lead to disagreements in the team environment.

Results:

Athletes become disciplined, but stress and anxiety levels increase due to psychological pressure.

A stable psychological environment is not formed in the team, and conflict situations may arise.

The level of trust between the coach and the athletes is low.

2. Liberal (lax) management style.

In a liberal management style, the coach grants great freedom to the athletes and intervenes minimally in the team's activities. In this method, the coach creates conditions for athletes to conduct independent training, enabling them to choose challenges and plan their own activities.

Psychological characteristics of liberal management:

Minimal control - the coach rarely intervenes directly in the athletes' activities.

Communication instability - the coach does not maintain sufficient demandingness when establishing contact with athletes.

Increasing independence - athletes have the opportunity to plan their sports activities during the training process.

Transferring leadership roles to athletes allows the coach to form informal leaders within the sports team and takes their opinions into account.

Results:

Athletes feel at ease, but often lack motivation and discipline.

A decline in team discipline and a slowdown in overall results are observed.

Since the coach does not manage the athletes individually, the team environment is not clearly formed.

3. Democratic style of government

The democratic management style is based on cooperation, mutual respect, and a free exchange of opinions between the coach and the athletes. The coach manages the athletes, taking into account their abilities and needs, while giving them independence.

Psychological characteristics of democratic governance:

Interaction - there is an open dialogue between the coach and the athletes.

Taking into account the individual abilities of athletes - the training process is conducted in accordance with the specific characteristics of the athletes.

Flexible management - the coach makes decisions taking into account the athletes' opinions and modifies training methods in accordance with their needs.

Emotional support - methods of encouragement are used to increase the motivation of athletes and ensure their mental stability.

Results:

A positive psychological climate is formed within the team, and the athletes' self-confidence increases.

The independence and initiative of athletes are developed.

Sports results improve in the long run, but the effectiveness of this method may decrease in cases where rapid growth and strict discipline are required.

The effectiveness of sports team management methods depends on their goals:

When strict discipline and rapid results are required, the autocratic method can yield high results in the short term but negatively affects the mental stability of athletes in the long term.

When it is necessary to increase the independence of athletes and develop creative thinking, the liberal style can be useful, but problems may arise in maintaining discipline.

When it is necessary to create a balanced development and a collective environment, the democratic style of governance is considered the most effective.

Experiments show that young athletes pay attention to the personal characteristics of their coaches. They form an attitude toward the coach based on his qualities, such as strictness or gentleness, fairness, kindness, and a sense of humor. In long-term cooperation, approaches that align with the needs and motivation of athletes will be more effective.

The management style of sports coaches directly influences the physical and psychological development of athletes. The coach's management style depends on the athletes' motivation, stress resistance, and stability of results; each style has its own advantages and disadvantages. Therefore, an effective coaching strategy must be developed taking into account the needs of athletes, temperament characteristics, and the overall goals of the team.

The research and practical activities of sports psychology cover various aspects. In general, its activities are divided into two main directions. The first direction is educational activity, aimed at increasing the level of psychological

readiness of athletes and coaches and teaching psychological methods, techniques, and strategies that serve to improve their results in competitions. Furthermore, this direction is linked to the development of coaches' knowledge and skills in the field of sports psychology.

The second direction is counseling, which is aimed at helping athletes overcome personal psychological problems. However, according to statistical research conducted in the UK, the share of sports psychologists engaged in this field is only 10%. This situation is primarily explained by the need for specialized clinical psychology to provide individual psychological assistance to athletes.

A sports psychologist adheres to the principles of general ethics in the process of implementing both directions of their activity—educational and advisory. These principles are characteristic of auxiliary professions, the main ones of which are: respect for human dignity and rights, professional competence, adherence to the principle of confidentiality, as well as not crossing one's professional boundaries. These principles ensure that sports psychology is conducted in practice in a scientifically grounded and ethical manner.

The principle of respecting human dignity and interests requires a sports psychologist to approach each athlete individually and take their psychological differences into account. In accordance with this principle, in some cases, it may be necessary for the psychologist to refrain from working with the athlete. In their research, Marchant and P. Gibbs analyzed the process of counseling a football player diagnosed with borderline personality disorder. Their research shows that when working with athletes with complex psychiatric problems, a sports psychologist must not exceed the scope of their qualifications and must understand that in such cases, it is necessary to refer them to an appropriate clinical psychologist or psychiatrist.

Thus, in sports psychology, adherence to professional ethical standards is an important factor in effective work with athletes, improving their psychological state, and ensuring their success in sports activities.

A sports coach is not only a specialist who manages an athlete's physical fitness but also exerts a significant influence on their psychological development. Every athlete has their own individual characteristics, and their mental state, level of motivation, stress resistance, and personal qualities determine their results in sports. From this perspective, the coach should be viewed as a leader who manages the athlete's psychological growth. His pedagogical approach, personality, and communicative abilities serve as decisive factors in an athlete's success.

The relationship between a coach and an athlete is a complex psychological process in which motivation, discipline, trust, and communication play an important role. A coach must correctly understand the psychological needs of their student, approach them according to their inner world, and conduct educational activities taking into account their personal characteristics. For example, while some athletes respond positively to a rigid leadership and authoritarian style of governance, others benefit more from a democratic approach based on freedom and trust. Therefore, it is important for the coach to develop an appropriate approach, taking into account the athlete's temperament type, volitional qualities, and emotional stability.

In sports psychology, the issue of stress and psychological pressure also requires special attention. Along with training the athlete in physical fitness, the coach must teach them to control themselves under psychological pressure, to accept defeat and learn from it, not to lose motivation, and to maintain confidence in their own strength in competitive conditions. Relaxation techniques, autogenic exercises, and breath control methods can be used as effective tools to manage stress that arises in athletes before competitions.

The coach also plays an important role in the formation of the psychological environment in sports teams. In team sports, the coach must foster team spirit by strengthening trust, mutual respect, and cooperation among athletes. If the competition within the team becomes too intense, or some athletes underestimate themselves, which can negatively impact team outcomes. Therefore, the coach must manage not only the individual but also the collective psychological environment. The psychological knowledge and approaches of sports coaches have a direct impact not only on athletes' athletic success but also on their personal development. A modern coach should be not only a coach who teaches physical exercises but also a psychological leader who fosters the mental stability, motivation, and social competencies of athletes. Therefore, the pedagogical and psychological training of sports coaches should be considered an important factor directly influencing the personal and professional development of an athlete.

Sports coaching is not only the organization of physical training but also the process of managing the formation and psychological development of an athlete's personality. A mentor plays a crucial role in developing their student's mental stability, motivation, stress resistance, and personal qualities. Therefore, a modern sports coach, along with pedagogical knowledge, must possess a deep understanding of sports psychology.

An athlete's success largely depends on their personal qualities, psychological resilience, and willpower. The coach must help develop these qualities and prepare the athlete physically and mentally for competitions. It is important that he chooses an appropriate approach, taking into account the individuality of the athlete's personality, and fully reveals their potential in sports activities.

Also, one of the coach's tasks is to create a healthy psychological environment in sports teams and to develop mutual trust and cooperation among athletes. If an athlete is under individual or collective psychological pressure, it can negatively impact their results. Therefore, a coach should act not only as a specialist who teaches sports techniques but also as a motivational leader and psychological supporter.

In general, a sports coach is one of the key factors in the development of an athlete's personality. It shapes not only the athlete's physical fitness but also their psychological stability, self-confidence, and drive for success. Therefore, sports coaching should always be viewed as a profession that requires a striving for pedagogical, psychological, and methodological excellence. Only through a comprehensive approach can a coach effectively work with their athletes and create the foundation for their success in sports and in life.

References:

1. Yuri Hanin. Individual zones of optimal functioning in sports.
2. Robert Yerkes, John Dodson. The relationship between stimulus strength and the speed of habit formation.
3. Weinberg R., Gould D. Foundations of Sports and Exercise Psychology.
- Spielberger C. Theory and research on anxiety.
5. Karimov F.A. Fundamentals of Sports Psychology. - Tashkent, 2020.

